

DESCRIPTIVE APPROXIMATION OF THE ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF JOURNALS ORBIS AND NEGOTIUM

APROXIMACIÓN DESCRIPTIVA DEL DESEMPEÑO ORGANIZACIONAL DE LAS REVISTAS ORBIS Y NEGOTIUM

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ABSTRACT

The article presents a descriptive approach to the organizational performance of the scientific journals Orbis and Negotium. The methodology was based on the research of the hemerographic sources existing on the web. The records were identified and processed by downloads. Indexing, evaluation, recommendation, appointments and visits via clustmaps. They were recorded in control cards, processed manually and digitally to build tables, diagrams and charts. As a corollary we have that Orbis and Negotium totalize according to Redalyc more than 400,000 downloads from 2013 to 2016; authors from Mexico, Venezuela, Nicaragua, Spain, Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Cameroon, Sri Lanka, Turkey, Indonesia and India having as main consumers Venezuela, Mexico, Germany, the United States, China and Peru, those located between the journals of greater push and organizational performance in the scientific area in the global context.

Keywords: organizational performance, scientific area; scientific journal.

RESUMEN

El artículo presenta una aproximación descriptiva del desempeño organizacional de las revistas científicas Orbis y Negotium. La metodología se basó en la pesquisa de las fuentes hemerográficas existentes en la web. Se identificaron y procesaron los registros por descargas. Indexación, evaluación, recomendación, citas y visitas vía clustmaps. Se registraron en fichas de control, se procesaron de forma manual y digital para construir las tablas, esquemas y gráficos. Como corolario tenemos que Orbis y Negotium totalizan según Redalyc más de 400.000 descargas de 2013 a 2016; autores procedentes de México, Venezuela, Nicaragua, España, Argentina, Brasil, Colombia, Cameroon, Sri Lanka, Turkey, Indonesia e India teniendo como principales consumidores Venezuela, México, Alemania, Estados Unidos, China y Perú, que las ubicadas entre las revistas de mayor empuje y desempeño organizacional en el área científica en el contexto mundial.

Palabras clave: desempeño organizacional, área científica; revistas científicas.

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METHODOLOGY AND BASIC DEFINITIONS

The methodology is descriptive based on the research and collection of the existing newspaper sources on the web, namely Redalyc.org, Academic Search Premier, Academic Plus, IBZ Online, Dialnet, Latindex and Latindex Catalog, Doaj, Erihplus, Class, Actualidad Iberoamericana, MIAR and Emerging Sources Citation Index among others. The records were identified and processed by downloads, indexing, evaluation, recommendation, appointments and visits via clustmaps. They were recorded in control cards, processed manually and digitally to build tables, diagrams and charts. The records for the journals were made individually, as well as the presentation of the same.

For purposes of the research is understood as organizational performance the different measurements of identification, registration, downloads, indexing, assessments, recommendations, appointments and visits exposed directly or indirectly on the website of scientific journals by academia, repositories and international indexes to standardize and standardize world quality and scientific production.

NEGOTIUM

Is a scientific journal, electronic, refereed. It is published three times a year, and is dedicated to the study and promotion of Management Science. Publish articles and studies on related fields such as: Communication, Psychology, Sociology, Political Science, Education, Ethics, Philosophy, History, Administration and Management. Prefers interdisciplinary contributions, with emphasis on business development, the problems of coexistence, communication and the creation of wealth.

Negotium 12 years / 36 issues / 155 articles / authors from Venezuela, Mexico, Spain, Nicaragua, Argentina, Indonesia and India. With an average of 7,000 monthly downloads from Mexico, the United States, China, Venezuela, Peru, among others.

Downloads per month Negotium Journal from 2013 to 2016

Month	2013	2014	2015	2016
January	2.612	2.583	3.884	3.595
February	603	3.221	3.734	5.895
March	1.278	4.410	4.452	5.468
April	1.481	3.523	3.488	6.121
May	1.581	4.535	6.747	7.734
Jun	1.670	3.876	4.667	5.901
July	1.526	2.811	3.856	4.506
August	2.135	3.215	3.426	4.910

Month	2013	2014	2015	2016
September	2.177	3.846	10.686	6.368
October	2.888	5.042	6.538	5.600
November	3.027	4.712	5.708	6.640
December	1.863	2.983	2.697	3.228
Total Annual	24.854	46.771	61.898	67.982

Source: Redalyc.org

Downloads Negotium Journal by Country

Country	Downloads
Mexico	19.213
United States	18.524
China	4.215
Venezuela	3.131
Peru	2.927
Others	15.357

Source: Redalyc.org

Negotiumis indexed in:

Index	Institution	Description
<u>Academic Search Premier</u>	EBSCO	A popular resource found in many scholarly settings worldwide, Academic Search Premier is a leading multidisciplinary research database. It provides acclaimed full-text journals, magazines and other valuable resources.
<u>Fuente Académica Plus</u>	EBSCO	This full-text database offers Spanish- and Portuguese-language academic content for researchers studying a broad range of disciplines. The extensive collection of scholarly journals and quality titles from Latin America, Portugal and Spain are readily available in PDF format.
<u>IBZ Online</u>	German National Library	The bibliography IBZ has been the leading international and interdisciplinary reference work documenting academic periodical literature in the humanities, social sciences and related fields for over a hundred years. The spectrum of subjects covered is unrivalled: in no other database are academic journals from so many fields covered.
<u>Doaj</u>	Open Society Institute	Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) is a community-curated online directory that indexes and provides access to high quality, open access, peer-reviewed journals.
<u>Dialnet</u>	De La Rioja University Dialnet Foundation	Dialnet is one of the largest bibliographic portals in the world, whose main task is to give greater visibility to the Hispanic scientific literature. Focusing primarily on the areas of Human, Legal and Social Sciences, Dialnet is constituted as a fundamental tool for the search of quality information.

Negotium is evaluated in:

Index	Institution	Description
<u>Doaj</u>	Open Society Institute	Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) is a community-curated online directory that indexes and provides access to high quality, open access, peer-reviewed journals.
<u>ERIHPlus</u>	NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data	The European Reference Index for the Humanities and the Social Sciences (ERIH PLUS) is an index containing bibliographic information on academic journals in the humanities and social sciences.
<u>Latindex</u> (Catalogue)	National Autonomous University of Mexico	Is based on the cooperation of a network of institutions that operate in coordination for the gathering and dissemination of relevant bibliographic information and editorial-quality criteria concerning the scientific serial publications produced in the region.
<u>Redalyc</u>	National Autonomous University of Mexico	Redalyc is an initiative of open access to the scientific production of the world in Ibero-American journals, which covers all areas of knowledge.
<u>Clase</u>	National Autonomous University of Mexico	Is a bibliographic database, which indexes academic journals of research, technical-professional and scientific or cultural diffusion, published in countries of Latin America and the Caribbean.
Actualidadiberoamericana	Centro de Información Tecnológica (CIT) Technological Information Center - Chile	International Index of journals published in Spanish, in several Ibero-American countries. Provides basic information about journals in various fields of science, engineering and the humanities, and categorized by areas of knowledge.
<u>MIAR</u>	Universitat de Barcelona - Spain	MIAR collects data for the identification and the analysis of scientific journals. Updated annually, MIAR gathers key data for identification and analysis of journals. These are grouped into major scientific areas -subdivided turn in more specialist academic fields. The system creates a matrix of correspondence between journals, identified by ISSN, and databases, directories and library catalogs that indexed or included.

It is also recommended by:

- Newsletters e-Government Forum OAS, edition 62, April 2011, page 21.
- Guide to e-Resources Specialized in Electronic Government and Public Administration of the Utemvirtual Library of the Universidad Tecnológica Metropolitana del Estado de Chile (UTEM). Page 86

- [Blog Economía y desarrollo económico internacional](#), this blog in Spanish presents data and analysis of interest of international economy, with special reference to Europe, countries of the OECD and Latin America. It is complementary to the World Development Blog of the Association of Euro-American Economic Development Studies and to the Economic Studies of International Development (EEDI) journal.
- [Portal de Revistas Electrónicas-Universidad de Carabobo](#), Is a platform designed for the dissemination of professional scientific journals published in full at the University of Carabobo, Venezuela.

The articles published by Negotium have quotes from important social scientists, such as:

- [The Routledge Companion to Consumer Behavior Analysis](#) edited by Gordon R. Foxall, page 227
- [Reinventar el negocio: Para vender más barato \(o más caro\)](#)writtenbyJosep-Francesc Valls.
- [Beyond the Low Cost Business: Rethinking the Business Model](#), JosepFrancescVallsGiménez.

In addition of the management and the commitment to disseminate and distribute science, has achieved that Negotium or the published articles in it, be in:

- [Directorio de Revistas especializadas en Comunicación del Portal de la Comunicación InCom-UAB](#)
- University of Rochester Libraries
- [Journals in Electronic Format-UNC-Chapel Hill Libraries](#)
- www.library.georgetown.edu
- www.ohiolink.edu
- www.dowling.edu
- www.mylibrary.library.nd.edu
- www.journalfinder.uncg.edu
- [Yokohama National University Library](#)
- Korea FoundationAdvanced Library
- www.ebscokorea.co.kr

- www.lib.ynu.ac.jp
- TheEuropeanLibrary
- [Polish Scholarly Bibliography \(PBN\)](http://PolishScholarlyBibliography(PBN))
- [Universitè de Caen Basse-Normandie /](http://UniversitèdeCaenBasse-Normandie/)
- SICD-Rèseau des Bibliothèques de L'Universitè
- Base d'Information Mutualiste sur les Périodiques Electroniques Joseph Fourier et de L'Institutè National Polytechnique de Grenoble
- www.ifremer.fr
- www.unicaen.fr
- [www.docelec.scd.univ-paris-diderot.fr /](http://www.docelec.scd.univ-paris-diderot.fr/)
- www.lettres.univ-lemans.fr
- www.bordeaux1.fr
- fr.dokupedia.org/index
- www.rzblx3.uni-regensburg.de
- www.rzblx1.uni-regensburg.de
- www.opac.sub.uni-goettingen.de
- www.blackboard.ccn.ac.uk
- [British Library](http://BritishLibrary)
- www.library.yorku.ca
- www.celat.ulaval.ca
- www.library.acadiau.ca
- www.bib.umontreal.ca
- www.scu.edu.au
- www.biblio.vub.ac
- www.bu.uni.wroc.pl
- www.cvtisr.sk
- www.jinfo.lub.lu.se
- www.brury.uonbi.ac.ke
- [www.bu.u-www.](http://www.bu.u-www)
- www.biblioteca.ibt.unam.mx
- phoenicis.dgsca.unam.mx
- www.phoenicis.dgsca.unam.mx
- www.liber-accion.org
- www.sid.uncu.edu.ar
- www.mediacioneducativa.com.ar
- www.sid.uncu.edu.ar
- [Biblioteca OEI](http://BibliotecaOEI)
- www.aladin.wrlc.org
- Www.nsd.org
- www.worldcatlibraries.org
- www.science.oas.org / [infocyt /](http://infocyt/)

- www.redhucyt.oas.org
- www.science.oas.org
- www.psicopedagogia.com
- <http://www.uce.resourcelinker.com>
- www.altavista.com
- [JournalTocs](#)
- [Biblioteca virtual Universidad Miguel de Cevantes](#)
- [Copac](#)
- [Portal de la Comunicación InCom-UAB](#)
- [Tecana American University](#)
- [Base de Datos Revistas de Gerencia UCAB](#)
- [Cite Factor](#)
- [Portal de Revistas Electrónicas de la Universidad de Carabobo](#)
- [Red Iberoamericana de Innovación y Conocimiento Científico](#)
- [Electronic Journal Library](#)
- [Index Compernicus](#)
- [Orbis Yale University Library Catalog](#)
- [Georgetown Law Library](#)
- [Bibliografía Latinoamericana en revistas de investigacioncientifica y social](#)
- [Biblioteca Universidad Nacional de Cordoba](#)
- [Conhecimento e Ciencia](#)
- [De Gerencia](#)
- [Centro de Información Tecnológica](#)
- [Clasificación de revistas arbitradas de Hispanoamérica y España en el área de administración de empresas](#)
- [Biblioteca Universidad Justo Sierra](#)
- [Compartiendo Experiencias Universitarias](#)
- [Global Impact Factor](#)
- [University of Saskatchewan](#)
- [UTS Library](#)
- [SEDICI](#)
- [University of Zurich](#)
- [Babord - Toute la documentation des universités de Bordeaux](#)
- [Toronto Public Library](#)
- [University of New Brunswick](#)
- [Biblioteca de la Universidad de Wroclaw](#)
- [German National Library of Science and Technology](#)
- [EKP publications](#)
- [University of Texas at El Paso](#)
- [Stanford UniversityLibraries](#)
- [CCG-IBT](#)

- SERIUNAM- Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México - Dirección General de Bibliotecas
- CLASE. Citas Latinoamericanas en Ciencias Sociales y Humanidades
- University of Rochester Library
- WorldCat
- Bibliothèques - Université de Toulouse
- Réseau des bibliothèques de l'Université Joseph Fourier et de Grenoble INP

Visits to the site www.revistanegotium.org.ve, from 10/01/2015 to 05/02/2017

	2015	2016	2017
January	N/D	556	4238
February	N/D	615	4752
March	N/D	614	3216
April	N/D	829	2446
May	N/D	1166	128
Jun	N/D	1428	N/D
July	N/D	1050	N/D
August	N/D	1843	N/D
September	N/D	1543	N/D
October	90	1001	N/D
November	663	1875	N/D
December	523	2330	N/D
Total annual	1.276	14850	14850

Source: from 10/01/2015 to 02/15/2017

<https://clustrmaps.com/map/Revistanegotium.org.ve>, from 02/16/2017 to 05/01/2017 <https://clustrmaps.com/site/18swf>

Visits by country to the site www.revistanegotium.org.ve from 02/16/2017 to 05/01/2017

Country	Visits
Venezuela	6,721
Mexico	619
Colombia	616

Country	Visits
United States	436
El Salvador	215
Ecuador	179
Peru	151
Honduras	128
Spain	122
United Kingdom	95
Argentina	81
Guatemala	68
Chile	49
Cuba	36
Canada	26
Australia	19
Costa Rica	19
Malaysia	16
Germany	14
India	12
Uruguay	11
Puerto Rico	10
Russia	10
Paraguay	10
Switzerland	9
Japan	7
Brazil	6
Nicaragua	6
France	5
Dominican Republic	5
Netherlands	4
Morocco	4
Sweden	4
Singapore	3
Ukraine	3
East Timor	3
Czech Republic	2
China	2
Taiwan	2
Slovak Republic	2
New Zealand	2
Bolivia	2

Country	Visits
South Africa	1
Pakistan	1
Italy	1
Iran	1

Source: <https://clustrmaps.com/site/18swf>

ORBIS

It is a scientific journal, electronic, refereed. It is published three times a year, and is dedicated to the study and promotion of Social Disciplines: Education Science, History, Philosophy, Political Science, Psychology, linguistics, Management, Sociology, Ethics

Orbis 12 years / 36 issues / 164 articles / authors from Venezuela, Spain, Mexico, Brazil, Colombia, Germany, Cameroon, Sri Lanka, India, Turkey, among others. With an average of 6,000 monthly downloads from Mexico, USA, China, Germany, Venezuela, Japan, among others.

Downloads per month OrbisJournal from 2013 to 2016

Month	2013	2014	2015	2016
January	2.632	2.711	3.867	3.779
February	685	3.406	3.947	6.047
March	1.340	4.887	5.213	0
April	1.343	3.774	3.509	6.284
May	1.520	4.504	6.402	7.622
Jun	1.415	4.580	4.876	5.290
July	1.481	3.451	3.966	4.255
August	2.357	3.610	3.598	4.404
September	2.306	4.165	11.074	5.223
October	3.150	5.204	6.818	5.008
November	3.405	4.575	5.529	6.150
December	2.179	2.916	2.726	2.919
Total Annual	25.826	49.797	63.540	58.997

Source: Redalyc.org

Downloads Orbis Journal by Country

Country	Downloads
Mexico	17.997
United States	17.976
China	4.456
Germany	2.922
Venezuela	2.829
Others	13.709

Source: Redalyc.org

Orbis indexed in:

Index	Institution	Description
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Index	Institution	Description
<u>Emerging Sources Citation Index</u>	Thomson Reuters	It is accessible through the Web of Science. The index includes academic journals of regional importance and in emerging scientific fields.
<u>Academic Search Premier</u>	EBSCO	A popular resource found in many scholarly settings worldwide, Academic Search Premier is a leading multidisciplinary research database. It provides acclaimed full-text journals, magazines and other valuable resources.
<u>Fuente Academica Plus</u>	EBSCO	This full-text database offers Spanish- and Portuguese-language academic content for researchers studying a broad range of disciplines. The extensive collection of scholarly journals and quality titles from Latin America, Portugal and Spain are readily available in PDF format.
<u>IBZ Online</u>	German National Library	The bibliography IBZ has been the leading international and interdisciplinary reference work documenting academic periodical literature in the humanities, social sciences and related fields for over a hundred years. The spectrum of subjects covered is unrivalled: in no other database are academic journals from so many fields covered.
<u>Doaj</u>	Open Society Institute	Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) is a community-curated online directory that indexes and provides access to high quality, open access, peer-reviewed journals.
<u>Dialnet</u>	De La Rioja University Dialnet Foundation	Dialnet is one of the largest bibliographic portals in the world, whose main task is to give greater visibility to the Hispanic scientific literature. Focusing primarily on the areas of Human, Legal and Social Sciences, Dialnet is constituted as a fundamental tool for the search of quality information.

Orbis is evaluated in:

Index	Institution	Description
<u>Doaj</u>	Open Society Institute	Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) is a community-curated online directory that indexes and provides access to high quality, open access, peer-reviewed journals.
<u>ERIHPlus</u>	NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data	The European Reference Index for the Humanities and the Social Sciences (ERIH PLUS) is an index containing bibliographic information on academic journals in the humanities and social sciences.

Index	Institution	Description
<u>Latindex</u> (Catalogue)	National Autonomous University of Mexico	Is based on the cooperation of a network of institutions that operate in coordination for the gathering and dissemination of relevant bibliographic information and editorial-quality criteria concerning the scientific serial publications produced in the region.
<u>Redalyc</u>	National Autonomous University of Mexico	Redalyc is an initiative of open access to the scientific production of the world in Ibero-American journals, which covers all areas of knowledge.
<u>Clase</u>	National Autonomous University of Mexico	Is a bibliographic database, which indexes academic journals of research, technical-professional and scientific or cultural diffusion, published in countries of Latin America and the Caribbean.
<u>MIAR</u>	Universitat de Barcelona - Spain	MIAR collects data for the identification and the analysis of scientific journals. Updated annually, MIAR gathers key data for identification and analysis of journals. These are grouped into major scientific areas - subdivided turn in more specialist academic fields. The system creates a matrix of correspondence between journals, identified by ISSN, and databases, directories and library catalogs that indexed or included.

Orbis is recognized, indexed, cataloged or reviewed in:

- REVENCYT
- IBT-CCG UNAM
- Directorio de Revistas especializadas en Comunicación del Portal de la Comunicación InCom-UAB
- www.cvtisr.sk
- www.journalfinder.uncg.edu
- Yokohama National University Library
- www.nsd.org
- University of Rochester Libraries
- Korea Foundation Advanced Library
- www.worldcatlibraries.org
- www.science.oas.org
- www.redhucyt.oas.org
- fr.dokupedia.org/index
- www.lib.ynu.ac.jp
- www.jinfo.lub.lu.se
- Université de Caen Basse-Normandie

- [SICD-Rèseau des Bibliothèques de L'Université](#)
- [Base d'InformationMutualiste sur les Périodiques Electroniques Joseph Fourier et de L'Institutè National Polytechnique de Grenoble](#)
- [Biblioteca OEI](#)
- [www.sid.uncu.edu.ar](#)
- [www.ifremer.fr](#)
- [www.unicaen.fr](#)
- [Journals in Electronic Format-UNC-Chapel Hill Libraries](#)
- [www.science.oas.org](#)
- [www.biblioteca.ibt.unam.mx](#)
- [www.library.georgetown.edu](#)
- [www.scholar.google.com](#)
- [www.altavista.com](#)
- [www.dowling.edu](#)
- [www.uce.resourcelinker.com](#)
- [www.biblioteca.ibt.unam.mx](#)
- [www.biblio.vub.ac](#)
- [www.opac.sub.uni-goettingen.de](#)
- [www.ohiolink.edu](#)
- [www.scu.edu.au](#)
- [www.docelec.scd.univ-paris-diderot.fr](#)
- [www.lettres.univ-lemans.fr](#)
- [www.bu.uni.wroc.pl](#)
- [www.cvtisr.sk](#)
- [www.library.acadiau.ca](#)
- [www.mylibrary.library.nd.edu](#)
- [www.brury.uonbi.ac.ke](#)
- [www.bordeaux1.fr](#)
- [www.ucab.edu.ve](#)
- [phoenicis.dgsca.unam.mx](#)
- [www.ebscokorea.co.kr](#)
- [www.rzblx3.uni-regensburg.de](#)
- [www.phoenicis.dgsca.unam.mx](#)
- [www.liber-accion.org](#)
- [www.mediacioneducativa.com.ar](#)
- [www.library.yorku.ca](#)
- [www.psicopedagogia.com](#)
- [www.sid.uncu.edu.ar](#)
- [www.fundacionunamuno.org.ve/revistas/](#)
- [www.aladin.wrlc.org](#)
- [www.blackboard.ccn.ac.uk](#)

- www.rzblx1.uni-regensburg.de
- www.celat.ulaval.ca
- www.bib.umontreal.ca

Visits to the site www.revistaorbis.org.ve, from 10/01/2015 to 05/02/2017

	2015	2016	2017
January	N/D	478	732
February	N/D	550	2.488
March	N/D	491	3.989
April	N/D	672	2.468
May	N/D	775	152
Jun	N/D	1.014	N/D
July	N/D	927	N/D
August	N/D	1.680	N/D
September	N/D	1.653	N/D
October	115	1.353	N/D
November	504	1.006	N/D
December	421	600	N/D
Total annual	1.040	11.199	9.829

Source: from 10/01/2015 to 02/15/2017

<https://clustrmaps.com/map/Revistaorbis.org.ve>, from 02/16/2017 to 05/01/2017

<https://clustrmaps.com/site/18swj>

Visits by country to the site www.revistaorbis.org.ve from 02/16/2017 to 05/01/2017

Country	Visits
Venezuela	7,058
Colombia	669
United States	596
Mexico	575
Puerto Rico	216
Ecuador	195

Country	Visits
Spain	175
Brazil	139
Cuba	90
United Kingdom	60
Peru	55
Australia	55
Argentina	41
Sri Lanka	40
India	25
Canada	24
Germany	22
Dominican Republic	21
Denmark	20
Chile	17
Nicaragua	13
Russia	11
Belgium	8
France	7
Sweden	7
Japan	7
Finland	6
Bolivia	6
Pakistan	6
Costa Rica	6
Singapore	4
El Salvador	3
China	3
Panama	3
Israel	3
Bulgaria	3
Switzerland	2
Morocco	2
Italy	2
Vietnam	2
Malaysia	2
Ukraine	1
Turkey	1
Saudi Arabia	1
Qatar	1

Country	Visits
Latvia	1
Ireland	1
Guatemala	1
Czech Republic	1
Bahrain	1

Source: <http://clustrmaps.com/site/18swj>

Fuentes

Redalyc.org,

[Academic Search Premier](#)

[Fuente Académica Plus](#)

[IBZ Online](#)

[Dialnet](#),

Latindex y

Latindex Catalogo,

Doaj,

Erihplus,

Clase, Actualida Iberoamericana,

MIAR y

Emerging Sources Citation Index

<http://clustrmaps.com>